

Data Management Cooperation in Practice: Lesson Learned

Pre-Conference Workshop

Odense, 6 July 2022

Topic:

Leveraging Synergies: Collaboration with other projects/initiatives: Skills4EOSC

Lightning Talk

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Today's Agenda

- What is Open Science ?
- European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) – The Purpose
- The SRIA Document – The Guide
- The EOSC Association Task Forces – The Brains
- Digital Skills: Skills4EOSC Project – The Mission
- Final Questions and Answers

What is Open Science?

An approach to the scientific process that focuses on spreading knowledge as soon as it is available using digital and collaborative technology. *

It means maximising the impact of research findings on Society also by disseminating scientific results to different targets and via different media

What is European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)?

- Environment for **hosting and processing research data to support EU Open Science**.
- Aims to **develop a trusted, virtual, federated environment that cuts across borders** and scientific disciplines to store, share, process, and re-use research digital objects (like publications, data, and software) following FAIR Data principles.
- **Brings together institutional, national and European stakeholders, initiatives, and data infrastructures** to develop an inclusive open science ecosystem in Europe.

This is expected to lead towards:

- **new insights and innovations**
- **higher research productivity and**
- **improved reproducibility in science.**

Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)

Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'

Standards, tools and services allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Sustainable and federated infrastructures enable open sharing of scientific results

EOSC-A Brain-Pool: 13 Task Forces

Implementation of EOSC

- Rules of Participation compliance monitoring
- PID policy and implementation
- Researcher engagement and adoption

Technical challenges on EOSC

- Technical interoperability of data and services
- Infrastructure for quality research software
- AAI Architecture

Metadata and data quality

- Semantic interoperability
- FAIR metrics and data quality

Research careers and curricula

- Data stewardship curricula and career paths
- Research careers, recognition and credit
- Upskilling countries to engage in EOSC

Sustaining EOSC

- Financial sustainability
- Long-term data preservation

Four key priority areas have been identified from the SRIA document, in line with the development of EOSC:

- 1. Developing the next generation of Open Science and data professionals;**
- 2. Coordinating training and aligning curricula for students and researchers;**
- 3. Building a trusted and long-lasting knowledge hub of learning materials and related tools;**
- 4. Influencing national Open Science policy for skills by supporting strategic leaders.**

Skills4EOSC – The Basics

Response to a related call ([INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-01](#))

Consortium Led by: [GARR \(Italy\)](#) with 44 partner institutions

Starting Date: [2022-09](#)

Focus on OS skills – core objective:

Skills for the European Open Science commons: creating a training ecosystem for Open and FAIR science

"...advance Open Science (OS) skills by unifying the current training landscape into a common and trusted pan-European ecosystem, closing the four gaps identified in the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) in relation to OS competences: lack of Open Science and data expertise, lack of a clear definition of data professional profiles and corresponding career paths, and fragmentation in training resources."

Skills4EOSC Figures

- 44 participants, 18 Countries
- “key doers” in Open Science in their Country/Region/Domain
- 2 ESFRI Research Infrastructures
- 7 million budget, GARR is coordinator
- Starting on September 1st, 2022
- 3 years duration

EOSC Governance

- 4CH
- BlueCloud
- C-SCALE
- DICE
- DIOSI
- DISSCO
- EGI-ACE
- ENVRI-FAIR Cluster
- EOSC-Future
- EOSC-Life Cluster
- EOSC-Nordic
- EOSC-Pillar
- EOSCsecretariat.eu
- EOSC-Synergy
- ESCAPE Cluster
- EuroCC
- FAIR4FAIR
- ISPAS
- LAPSI
- Ni4OS Europe
- Norway: Shared infrastructure and services for FAIR data
- Open Science Link
- Openaire- Nexus
- PaNOSC Cluster
- RELIANCE
- SoBigData++
- SSHOC Cluster
- SUHF - WG for Open Science
- SYNTHESYS+
- TRIPLE
- UNITE.H2020

Projects

- EOSC Association
- EOSC Steering Board

Task Forces

- AAI Architecture
- Data Stewardship Curricula and Career Paths
- Defining Funding Models for EOSC
- FAIR Metrics and Data Quality
- Infrastructure for Quality Research Software
- Long-Term Data Preservation
- PID Policy and Implementation
- Research Careers, Recognition, and Credit
- Researcher Engagement and Adoption
- Rules of Participation Compliance Monitoring
- Semantic Interoperability
- Technical Interoperability of Data and Services
- Upskilling Countries to Engage in EOSC

Executive Board

- Architecture
- FAIR
- Landscape
- Rules of Participation
- Skills and Training
- Sustainability

WG

- ICDI Competence Center

Competence Center

- DOAB
- Dutch National Open Science Programme
- ESFRI
- European University Association
- JRC - Evidence Based Policy
- Research Data Netherlands
- TDWG Biodiversity Data Standards
- Universities Norway

Other

- Cesaer TF Open Science
- Community of Practice of Trainer Coordinators
- CONOSC
- CONPER
- Coordination Austrian EOSC M.O.
- EOSC Finnish Forum
- French Committee for Open science /the Skills and Training College
- G6 EU Network
- GAIA-X
- GO FAIR Austria office
- GO FAIR CO-OPERAS IN - FAIR Social Sciences and Humanities
- GO FAIR Implementation Network "Data Stewardship Competence Centers"
- International Network of Open Science Communities
- LIBER Citizen Science working group
- National RDM Network Denmark
- Norwegian Digitization strategy for higher education
- Norwegian National forum for open science
- Norwegian National strategy for openness and sharing of research data
- Open Science Community Sweden
- OpenAIRE
- RDA Biodiversity Data Integration IG
- RDA Denmark
- RDA ETHRD IG
- RDA France
- RDA Germany
- RDA Global
- RDA Norway
- RDA Professionalising Data Stewardship IG
- RDA Sweden
- Swedish Network for Evidence-Based Policy
- The Carpentries

Initiatives

Work Package Structure

What's in it for librarians and libraries?

The role of the librarian in the EOSC

It is not to be set apart but reinforced as a critical support role for research.

This reinforcement needs to be supported and empowered via adequate skills, lifelong learning, and understanding of specific tools and providing services.

Skills for Open Science professionals

Skills4EOSC will:

- Support institutional, disciplinary, and national communities to develop an EOSC-ready, digitally skilled workforce
 - Develop a “minimum viable skillset” for different stakeholders by charting a comprehensive map of varying career profiles and defining for each a set of minimum requirements for competencies and proficiency levels tailored to a specific Open Science professional profile
 - Design and develop Train of Trainer courses and learning paths targeting different professionals, including librarians
 - Define a methodology to ensure the realization of FAIR-by-design learning materials to sustain the training actions on Open Science and Research Data Management in Europe
 - Ensure continuous refresh and update of competencies through professional and thematic networks for lifelong learning.
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Unique support network

By leveraging on its unique consortium, Skills4EOSC will create a network of Open Science and Research Data Management competence centers that will:

- Foster the uptake of best practices and share of successful stories
- Create a European network of support on the Open Science and RDM themes
- Share useful tools and services
- Harmonize curricula and learning paths targeting researchers, data professionals and policy-makers

Not only just Open Science

Skills4EOSC is looking beyond Open Science to embrace linked topics:

- **Science for policy** - Increase the impact of research results on policy and society at large
- **Ethical, Legal and Social Issues** - Scientific research and technological development processes that take into account effects and potential impacts on the environment and society also from a legal and ethical perspective

Libraries in the EOSC: challenges

- Support all actors in the practice of Open Science (not only researchers, but also policy makers, funders, citizens)
- Drive the changes occurring in the current scholarly communication system (Diamond Open Access, new publication platforms as ORE, etc...)
- Support researchers and institutions in the upcoming reform of research assessment

Questions and Answers

Actors in the EOSC ecosystem: roles and interactions, Source: SRIA

